

THE EFFECT OF SERVICE REQUIREMENTS, SERVICE PROCEDURES, SERVICE TIME AND SERVICE RATES ON PUBLIC SATISFACTION AT THE ORGANIZATIONAL OFFICE OF THE BATAM CITY REGIONAL SECRETARIAT

Nurhasanah¹, Sabri², Sumardin³

^{1,2,3}Faculty Of Economics And Business, Universitas Ibnu Sina

Received : 15 January 2026

Published : 28 February 2026

Revised : 31 January 2026

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.54443/ijebas.v6i1.5339>

Accepted : 20 February 2026

Link Publish : <https://radjapublika.com/index.php/IJEBAS>

Abstract

This study aims to determine and analyze the influence of Service Requirements, Service Procedures, Service Time, and Service Rates on Public Satisfaction at the Organizational Section of the Regional Secretariat of Batam City. The research method used is a quantitative method with a survey approach. The population in this study were the community who use services at the Organizational Section of the Regional Secretariat of Batam City, with a sample size of 100 respondents. The data collection technique was carried out through the distribution of questionnaires measured using a Likert scale. Data processing and analysis were carried out using the SPSS program. The results of the study indicate that simultaneously Service Requirements, Service Procedures, Service Time, and Service Rates have a positive and significant effect on Public Satisfaction, as evidenced by the F-count value of 90.847 which is greater than the F-table of 2.47 and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05. Partially, Service Requirements have a significant effect on Public Satisfaction with a t-count value of 9.712 > t-table 1.985 and a significance of 0.000 < 0.05. Service Procedures also have a significant effect on Public Satisfaction with a t-count value of 16.113 > t-table 1.985 and a significance of 0.000 < 0.05. Service Time has a significant effect on Public Satisfaction with a t-count value of 6.482 > t-table 1.985 and a significance of 0.000 < 0.05. Furthermore, Service Rates have the most dominant and significant influence on Public Satisfaction with a t-count value of 17.603 > t-table 1.985 and a significance of 0.000 < 0.05. Thus, it can be concluded that improving service quality in all aspects will have an impact on increasing public satisfaction.

Keywords: Service Requirements, Service Procedures, Service Hours, Rates Service to Community Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Public service is one of the primary functions of government, directly related to the public interest. Local governments, as part of the state administration, are responsible for providing quality, effective, efficient, transparent, and public satisfaction-oriented services. The success of a government is measured not only by its ability to implement development programs, but also by the extent to which it delivers public services that meet the needs and expectations of the community. Therefore, the quality of public service is a crucial indicator of good governance. In the context of regional government, public services encompass various activities carried out by regional government agencies, including administrative services, licensing, and information services. One work unit that plays a strategic role in fostering, supervising, and controlling the quality of public services in the region is the Organizational Section of the Batam City Regional Secretariat. This unit serves as a driving force for bureaucratic reform, particularly in improving the quality of public services through evaluation of service delivery across all regional government agencies (OPD). Batam City, as a metropolitan city and center of economic growth in the Riau Islands Province, has a high level of public service dynamics. Rapid population growth, industrial development, and intensive trade activity demand fast, easy, and high-quality public services. Batam residents are increasingly critical and have high expectations of government services, both in terms of speed, procedural clarity, and affordability. This situation requires every government agency, including the Organizational Section of the Batam City Regional Secretariat, to continuously improve public service standards in accordance with Regulation of the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform (Permenpan RB) Number 15 of 2021 concerning Guidelines for Public Service Standards.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Description This theoretical review includes a description of the theory, research that aligns with the rationale behind the research. The theoretical description contains theories related to the research topic, which aim to strengthen the research being conducted.

Service Procedures Service procedures are a series of steps or stages that must be followed in the process of providing services to the public, from the request stage to the completion of the service. In the context of public administration, service procedures serve as operational guidelines to ensure that each service is provided consistently, promptly, transparently, and in accordance with established standards. Well-organized procedures minimize administrative errors, prevent irregularities, and improve service efficiency. According to the Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform (2021), service procedures are standardized procedures for service providers and recipients in the public service delivery process.

Service Rates Service fees are a crucial element in the provision of public services, reflecting the government's responsibility to uphold the principles of transparency, accountability, and fairness in charging fees to the public. Generally, service fees can be defined as the amount the public must pay in exchange for services provided by government agencies, in accordance with statutory provisions. According to the Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform (2021), public service tariffs are fees determined based on the cost components incurred by service providers in providing services to the public. Tariff determination must consider the principles of fairness, propriety, efficiency, transparency, and affordability to avoid placing an undue burden on the public as service users.

Previous Research The following table is a summary of the results of previous research relevant to the variables of service requirements, service procedures, service times, and service rates on public satisfaction.

Research Framework To determine the influence of Service Requirements, Service Procedures, Service Times, and Service Rates on Public Satisfaction, a framework was created that explains the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variables in this study.

Research Hypothesis

1. There is an influence of Service Requirements on Public Satisfaction at the Organizational Section Office of the Batam City Regional Secretariat.
2. There is an influence of Service Procedures on Public Satisfaction at the Organizational Section Office of the Batam City Regional Secretariat.
3. There is an influence of Service Time on Public Satisfaction at the Organizational Section Office of the Batam City Regional Secretariat.
4. There is an influence of Service Rates on Public Satisfaction at the Organizational Section Office of the Batam City Regional Secretariat

METHOD

Location and Time Study This research was conducted by the author in order to examine the problem of consumer satisfaction at the organizational section of the Batam City Regional Secretariat office located at Jl. Engku Putri No. 1 Batam Center, Riau Islands.

Population According to Sugiyono (2020:80), a population is a generalized area consisting of objects or subjects with certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions drawn. A population is all the elements that will serve as data sources in a study. In line with this opinion, Herlina and Putra (2021:54) explain that the population is not only limited to people, but also includes all units of analysis such as institutions, documents, events, or phenomena that are relevant to the research objectives. The population in this study was the public service users at the Organizational Section Office of the Batam City Regional Secretariat, totaling 23,250 people. The population consists of residents who received administrative and non-administrative services in various service units under the coordination of the Organizational Section Office of the Batam City Regional Secretariat during the past year. This population was chosen because it is considered representative of all service recipients and can provide objective assessments of service requirements, procedures, service times, and service rates provided by the local government. Therefore, this population is relevant for measuring public satisfaction (Y) as the dependent variable in the study.

Sample This technique was chosen because the population of service users at the Batam City Regional Secretariat Organizational Section Office is homogeneous, meaning they are all recipients of public services. Therefore, every individual in the population has an equal opportunity to be included in the research sample.

To determine the number of samples, the Slovin formula is used (Siregar, 2022:48) as follows

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Slovin's Formula

Information:

n = sample size

N = population size

e = sampling error level (error tolerance), in this study used 10% or 0.1

Based on population data of 23,250 people, the calculation is:

$$n = \frac{23.250}{1 + 23.250(10\%)^2}$$

$$\frac{23.250}{233,5} = 99.56 = 100 \text{ people}$$

Based on the calculation results, the number of samples was rounded to 100 respondents.

Operational Definition of Variables An operational definition of a variable is a clear explanation of each variable in a study and is broken down into indicators. Indicators are measurable dimensions. The following operational definitions are presented in a table.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results Study The Organizational Section Office is a work unit under the Batam City Regional Secretariat and plays a strategic role in supporting regional governance. This section focuses on institutional structure, governance development, and improving the quality of public services to achieve effective and efficient governance. As a staff element that assists the Regional Secretary, the Organizational Section is tasked with preparing policy formulations, coordinating, fostering, and controlling the implementation of tasks in the areas of government organization, governance, job analysis, workload analysis, and institutional administrative services. In carrying out its functions, the Organizational Section plays a vital role in ensuring that services to the public are implemented in accordance with established service standards, including service requirements, service procedures, service times, and service rates.

**Table Questionnaire Distribution
Case Processing Summary**

		N	%
Cases	Valid	100.0	100.0
	Excluded	.0	.0
	Total	100.0	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Source: Data processed in SPSS

Based on the sample calculation, the number of respondents determined for this study was 100 members of the public. Therefore, 100 copies of the questionnaire were distributed. Data collection results showed that all 100 distributed questionnaires were returned, and none were damaged or incomplete, allowing for further processing and analysis. Therefore, the number of respondents used in this study was 100.

Table Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity testing is performed to determine whether there is a high correlation between the independent variables in a regression model. A good regression model should not experience multicollinearity. Multicollinearity testing is performed by examining the Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values. If the Tolerance value is >0.10 and the VIF value is <10, it can be concluded that the regression model does not experience multicollinearity.

THE EFFECT OF SERVICE REQUIREMENTS, SERVICE PROCEDURES, SERVICE TIME AND SERVICE RATES ON PUBLIC SATISFACTION AT THE ORGANIZATIONAL OFFICE OF THE BATAM CITY REGIONAL SECRETARIAT

Nurhasanah et al

Coefficientsa

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	Terms of service	.256	3,907
	Service Procedures	.203	4,931
	Service Hours	.374	2,673
	Service Rates	.191	5,246

a. Dependent Variable: Community Satisfaction

Based on Table 4.7, it is known that the VIF value for each independent variable is as follows:

- The Service Requirements variable (X1) has a VIF value of 3.907 with a tolerance value of 0.256.
- The Service Procedure variable (X2) has a VIF value of 4.931 with a tolerance value of 0.203.
- The Service Time variable (X3) has a VIF value of 2.673 with a tolerance value of 0.374.
- The Service Rate variable (X4) has a VIF value of 5.246 with a tolerance value of 0.191.

Table Partial t-Test Results for Service Requirements Variable (X1)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6,622	3,763		1,760	.082
	Terms of service	.809	.083	.700	9,712	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Community Satisfaction

Source: Data processed in SPSS

Based on Table 4.8, the results of the partial t-test, the calculated t-value for the Service Requirements variable (X1) was 9.712 with a significance value of 0.000.

The hypothesis proposed in this study is:

- H_0 : Service requirements do not have a significant effect on public satisfaction.
- H_a : Service requirements have a significant effect on public satisfaction.

The decision making criteria are:

1. If $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$ at $\alpha = 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.
2. If $t \text{ count} < t \text{ table}$ at $\alpha = 0.05$, then H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected.

The t-table value is determined with a significance level of 5% and a two-sided test, with degrees of freedom (df) = $n - k - 1$, namely $100 - 4 - 1 = 95$. Based on the t-distribution table, the t-table value is 1.985.

Based on the multiple linear regression equation above, it can be explained as follows:

1. The constant value of 0.519 indicates that if the variables Service Requirements, Service Procedures, Service Time, and Service Rates are considered to have a value of zero, then Public Satisfaction has a value of 0.519.
2. The regression coefficient of the Service Requirements variable (X1) is 0.091 and has a positive sign, which means that every increase in Service Requirements will increase Public Satisfaction by 0.091 units, assuming that other variables are held constant.
3. The regression coefficient of the Service Procedure variable (X2) is 0.345 and has a positive sign, which means that the better the Service Procedure provided, the more Public Satisfaction will increase by 0.345 units, assuming other variables remain constant.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results and discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- 1) Service Requirements (X1) based on the results of the partial t-test (simple regression) have a positive and significant effect on Public Satisfaction (Y). This is indicated by a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a

THE EFFECT OF SERVICE REQUIREMENTS, SERVICE PROCEDURES, SERVICE TIME AND SERVICE RATES ON PUBLIC SATISFACTION AT THE ORGANIZATIONAL OFFICE OF THE BATAM CITY REGIONAL SECRETARIAT

Nurhasanah et al

calculated t-value of 9.712 > t-table 1.985, so it can be concluded that Service Requirements have a partial significant effect on Public Satisfaction.

- 2) Service Procedures (X2) based on the results of the partial t-test (simple regression) have a positive and significant effect on Public Satisfaction (Y). This is indicated by a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05 and a calculated t-value of 16.113 > t-table 1.985, so it can be concluded that Service Procedures have a partial significant effect on Public Satisfaction.
- 3) Service Time (X3) based on the results of the partial t-test (simple regression) has a positive and significant effect on Public Satisfaction (Y). This is indicated by a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05 and a calculated t-value of 6.482 > t-table 1.985, so it can be concluded that Service Time has a partial significant effect on Public Satisfaction.
- 4) Service Rates (X4) based on the results of the partial t-test (simple regression) have a positive and significant effect on Public Satisfaction (Y). This is indicated by a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05 and a calculated t-value of 17.603 > t-table 1.985, so it can be concluded that Service Rates have a significant partial effect on Public Satisfaction.
- 5) Based on the results of the F test (simultaneous), the variables of Service Requirements, Service Procedures, Service Time, and Service Rates together have a significant effect on Public Satisfaction. This is evidenced by the calculated F value of 90.847 > F table 2.47 and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, so that the regression model is declared feasible and significant.
- 6) Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis, the regression equation was obtained
$$Y=0.519+0.091X1+0.345X2-0.003X3+0.560X4$$
which shows that simultaneously all independent variables influence Public Satisfaction, with Service Rates (X4) and Service Procedures (X2) as the variables that have the most dominant influence in the multiple regression

SUGGESTION

Based on the research conclusions that have been obtained, the suggestions for the Batam City Regional Secretariat Organization Office include the following:

1. For the Organizational Section Office of the Batam City Regional Secretariat, it is hoped that it can continue to improve the quality of Service Requirements, especially in terms of clarity of requirements, ease of administrative fulfillment, and transparency of information to the public so that the services provided are easier to understand and access.
2. Service procedures need to be continuously simplified and their consistency improved so that the public can receive fast, clear, and standardized services. Increased dissemination of service procedures is also necessary to ensure the public understands the applicable service flow.
3. Service time should be a serious concern by improving the discipline of the apparatus, punctuality of service, and the use of information technology to speed up the service process for the public.
4. Service rates, as the most dominant variable influencing public satisfaction, must be managed transparently, fairly, and in accordance with applicable regulations. Clear information regarding rates and the appropriateness of costs and service quality are expected to further enhance public satisfaction.
5. For further researchers, it is recommended to add other variables outside this research, such as the quality of human resources, service facilities, or the use of information technology, in order to provide a more comprehensive picture of the factors that influence public satisfaction.

REFERENCES

- Adams, J. S. (2020). *Equity Theory of Motivation and Satisfaction in Public Administration*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Andini, R. (2023). The Influence of Administrative Requirements and Tariff Affordability on Public Satisfaction with Public Services in Banyuwangi Regency. *Journal of Public Administration*, 10(2), 45–56.
- Arikunto, S. (2021). *Research Procedures: A Practical Approach*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Dwiyanto, A. (2021). *Public Service Management in the Era of Regional Autonomy*. Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University Press.
- Dwiyanto, A. (2022). *Bureaucratic Reform and Public Service Performance*. Yogyakarta: UGM Press.

THE EFFECT OF SERVICE REQUIREMENTS, SERVICE PROCEDURES, SERVICE TIME AND SERVICE RATES ON PUBLIC SATISFACTION AT THE ORGANIZATIONAL OFFICE OF THE BATAM CITY REGIONAL SECRETARIAT

Nurhasanah et al

- Ghozali, I. (2020). *Multivariate Analysis Application with IBM SPSS 26 Program*. Semarang: Diponegoro University Publishing Agency.
- Ghozali, I. (2021). *Quantitative Research Methods for Management and Economics*. Semarang: BP Undip.
- Ghozali, I. (2022). *Statistical Analysis for Quantitative Research*. Semarang: Undip Press.
- Hardiansyah, H. (2020). *Public Service Quality: Concept, Dimensions, and Implementation*. Yogyakarta: Gava Media.
- Hardiansyah, H. (2022). *Public Services from the Perspective of Public Policy and State Administration*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Herlina, D., & Putra, A. (2021). *Social and Business Research Methodology*. Jakarta: Prenadamedia Group.
- Istijanto. (2005). *Human Resources Research*. Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Kasmir. (2022). *Public Service Management*. Jakarta: Rajawali Pers.
- Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform. (2020). *General Guidelines for Public Services*. Jakarta: Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform.
- Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform. (2021). *Public Service Standards and Implementation of Bureaucratic Reform in Indonesia*. Jakarta: Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2020). *Marketing Management (15th ed.)*. Pearson Education.
- Kreitner, R., & Kinicki, A. (2022). *Organizational Behavior (11th ed.)*. New York: McGraw-Hill Education.
- Lestari, N. (2022). Analysis of the Influence of Service Time and Cost on Public Satisfaction at the Bekasi Regency DPMPSTP. *Journal of Public Management*, 8(3), 12–22.
- Moore, M. (2022). *Public Value: Strategic Management in Government*. Harvard University Press.
- Nugraha, R. (2021). The Influence of Service Procedure Quality on Public Satisfaction at the Samsat Office of Riau Islands Province. *Journal of Public Policy*, 5(1), 66–74.
- Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, L. L. (2021). SERVQUAL: A Multiple-Item Scale for Measuring Consumer Perceptions of Service Quality. *Journal of Retailing*, 64(1), 12–40.
- Pratama, R. (2021). The Influence of Service Requirements and Service Procedures on Public Satisfaction at the Tanjungpinang Timur District Office. *Journal of Government Science*, 9(2), 33–45.
- Putri, E. (2022). The Effect of Service Rates and Processing Speed on Patient Satisfaction at the Tiban Baru Community Health Center, Batam City. *Journal of Health Administration*, 7(2), 77–85.
- Rahman, A. (2021). The Influence of Service Procedures and Tariffs on Service User Satisfaction at the Medan City Transportation Agency. *Journal of Public Services*, 6(4), 23–35.
- Rumengan, R. (2020). *Quantitative and Qualitative Research Methodology*. Manado: CV Indomedia Pustaka.
- Sari, D. (2020). The Influence of Service Standards and Service Time on Public Satisfaction at the Population and Civil Registration Service of Pekanbaru City. *Journal of Public Administration*, 6(1), 41–50.
- Siregar, S. (2022). *Parametric Statistics for Quantitative Research*. Jakarta: Kencana.
- Sugiyono. (2012). *Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D Research Methods*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Sugiyono. (2020). *Business Research Methods: Quantitative, Qualitative, and Combination Approaches*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Sugiyono. (2021). *Statistics for Research*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Tjiptono, F. (2021). *Service Marketing: Principles, Applications, and Research*. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset.
- Wibowo, A. (2020). *Public Satisfaction with Public Service Performance*. Jakarta: Rajagrafindo Persada.
- Wibowo, A. (2021). *Public Service Management Based on Public Satisfaction*. Jakarta: Mitra Wacana Media.
- Yuliana, D. (2020). The Influence of Service Procedures and Officer Attitudes on Public Satisfaction with Online Licensing Services in Batam City. *Journal of Regional Government*, 8(2), 14–24.